

COVID^X

The COVID-X programme is the European Acceleration Program for Data Solutions with the power to save LIVES from Covid-19 challenges!

[Read more about the programme](#)

Find out where the healthcare providers involved in the programme are!

[Check the map](#)

Watch the interview with SERMAS Clinical Ambassadors!

[Interview](#)

Our collaborations:

We work with a range of parallel projects in common areas of research to maximise our impact and network reach.

Have a look!

COVID-X

www.covid-x.eu / info@covid-x.eu

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